

REFUGEES AND HOST COMMUNITIES: THE PROBLEM OF SOCIAL INTEGRATION

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Abstract

The relevance of the chosen topic is explained by the fact that in the modern world, globalization processes are intensifying and related processes of mass migration. Other cultural, other ethnic population in the city, as a result of which problems began to arise with the reception, resettlement, employment, integration into social and cultural structure of the city of migrants and refugees. In 2015 to EU countries a huge stream of refugees poured in, and in general European countries coped with the acceptance and arrangement of such a number arriving population. Migration problems affect the interests of many countries, including Russia, they need to be solved jointly, developing unified policy and unified measures for the reception, resettlement and integration of migrants and refugees, ensuring their democratic rights and freedoms

Key words: refugees, conflict, migration

For the last two decades the number of people in the world, forcibly driven from their places, has increased significantly - to a stunning figure of 65.6 million people in 2016, and still remains record high. Only that year from their 10.3 million people were forced to leave their home - this means that every minute every day, an average of 20 people, under the influence of circumstances, were forced to leave their native places.

The processes of globalization increase the social significance of the phenomenon of migration flows in general and issues and tasks related to ensuring favorable

intercultural interaction between different peoples, in particular. Phenomenon migration flows have existed under different names since ancient times. Struggle for life in favorable climate conditions, for the possession of rich natural resources, optimal opportunities for economic activity determined the search, the conquest of new territories by peoples at the stage of formation of state formations.

European integration processes, the most active of which were observed in throughout the second half of the 20th century, set to the European Union (EU) key challenges such as free movement citizens under the regime of open borders, and the cost-effective functioning of its internal market. The issue of regulation of migration flows from third countries, including acquisitions refugee status, the priorities are not entered. The European approach to the integration of migrants into the host society, in our opinion, fundamentally different from Russian. Contrary to the constant statements of European officials and politicians about the formation of a single socio-economic and cultural space, the positions of countries regarding the reception and adaptation of migrants vary greatly. In the EU countries there is a tightening of border control and migration legislation.

However, in recent years, only fierce discussions have been observed everywhere on issues of accommodation, provision and legalization of emigrants. Economically less developed countries are trying to completely abandon them, leaving their neighbors to deal with the problems of adaptation of migrants. The population, some local political and public organizations are ambiguous about emigrants. Serious protest moods are manifested in Hungary, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland, the Baltic countries and Germany. The question of the economic adaptation of emigrants has hardly moved forward. This EU countries finance Turkey, which should not allow refugees into Europe.

The concept of 'integration' is a controversial concept used in different meanings by policy makers, academics, immigrants and the receiving society. As Castles have pointed out, there is no accepted definition or model of immigrant and refugee integration. Therefore, integration remains a controversial concept. Robinson, like Castles and others, stated that integration is a chaotic term and is used by many people

with different meanings. International migration policies are especially based on the adaptation of immigrants and refugees to the country they migrated to. However, as Faist points out, international migration is a multidimensional economic, political, cultural and demographic process that summarizes two or more positions in many nation-states with many ties, and the various ties between those who move and those who stay. Therefore, international migration is a complex phenomenon that should be evaluated within the process of social transformation.

The international migration process is a long-term process that includes the second and third generations, from the immigration decision of the immigrants to their settlement in the country they migrated to. The policies implemented to control international migration until the 1990s also included "integration", considering that immigrants were not "temporary". However, for some countries, controlling immigration has been more important than integration policies. International migration, especially irregular migration and forced migration, has become the most important issue that constitutes the political agenda in the world, both at the international and national level.

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According to the third article of this regulation, a refugee is a person who is outside the country of his/her nationality and cannot benefit from the protection of the country of which he/she is a citizen because he/she is rightfully afraid that he/she will be persecuted because of his/her race, religion, nationality, membership of a certain social group or political opinions due to events taking place in Europe. It is defined as

a foreigner who does not want to benefit from it because of his/her nationality or who does not want to return there if he/she is outside the country of his/her former residence or does not want to return due to his/her fear.

Again, according to the third article of the regulation adopted in 1994, an asylum seeker is a person who is outside the country of his/her nationality and cannot benefit from the protection of his/her country of citizenship because he/she is a rightful fear of being persecuted because of his/her race, religion, nationality, membership of a certain social group or political opinions. means a foreigner who does not want to or does not have a nationality and does not return there if he is outside the country of his former residence, or does not want to return because of fear". Turkey's 1994 regulation does not mention refugees and asylum seekers' right to health and access to social services.

Syria, with more than half of its population turned into internal or international refugees, remained the main source of refugees in 2016, which by the end of the year amounted to 5.5 million people. While 123 Syrian refugees were taken in countries on all six continents, 87% of them remained in countries bordering Syria. Most of the refugees accepted by Turkey (2.5 million), although other countries accepted large numbers of Syrians - Lebanon (1 million), Jordan (648,800), Iraq (230,800), and Egypt (116,000).

Forced displacement of people is a permanent phenomenon on the world landscape, and Europe here is no exception. Indeed, according to a UNHCR report "The refugee situation in the world in 2000: fifty years of humanitarian assistance", more than 40 million people were driven from their seats during the Second world war. Smaller but so no less significant populations have been displaced as a result of conflicts and political turmoil in subsequent decades.

The main component of the EU response on the chaotic arrival of migrants across the Aegean in the second half of 2015 and first quarter 2016 is a joint "statement" of the EU and Turkey, an agreement entered into force in March 2016. This arrangement was agreed directly by the Prime Minister Turkey and the Chancellor of Germany and presented to other chapters European states already accomplished fact.

In summary, we can conclude that the European approach to the integration of migrants into the host society is insufficiently coordinated and situational. Countries of the EU is trying to shift the problem of adaptation of emigrants to each other, aggravating the current situation, delaying the solution of accumulated problems.

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